

TEACHING ADVANCED QUANTITATIVE TECHNIQUES THROUGH A COMPETITIVE PROJECT

Bruno Domenech¹

Department of Management, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech
Barcelona, Spain

ORCID: 0000-0002-4332-2400

Alberto García-Villoria

Department of Management, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech
Barcelona, Spain

Javier Maquirriain

Department of Management, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech
Barcelona, Spain

Rafael Pastor

Department of Management, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya – BarcelonaTech
Barcelona, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Heuristics, metaheuristics and matheuristics are quantitative techniques that can be used to solve complex combinatorial optimisation problems for many engineering applications (industry, logistics, supply chain, scheduling, services, etc.). The course Quantitative Methods of Industrial Process Management II from the Master's Degree in Industrial Engineering of the Technical University of Catalonia addresses such topic. The course is organised into 3 session typologies: (1) master classes, where lecturers provide students the theoretical concepts; (2) practical classes, where students solve small-size problems based on real cases; and (3) competitive project, which is the core of the evaluation. On this regard, a real-based combinatorial optimisation problem is provided and, in 3-member groups, students have to develop an ad hoc (meta/math/hiper)heuristic, based on the theory concepts, and code it with standard language (Python, Java, C++, etc.). For the evaluation, each group solves 10 exam-instances of the problem. The qualification is based on the result achieved by each group for each instance in comparison with a minimum quality threshold, defined by the lecturers, and the results of the other groups. In this manner, students learn very complex concepts in a friendly but competitive environment, which invites them to work hard on the application of theory concepts into a problem close to those they will find in their professional career. Students' assessments show an increase in their performance and interest regarding the course.

¹ Bruno Domenech, bruno.domenech@upc.edu

1 INTRODUCTION

In last years, university education is using innovative methodologies to improve students' understanding, reasoning capacity or skills for problem-solving [1]. In particular, future engineers are expected to deal with multidisciplinary problems, requiring cross-curricular capacities [2]. Project Based Learning (PBL) is gaining attention [3]. Students adopt an active role, while addressing real-based motivating projects [4]. PBL has been adopted in many courses [5]; often using a gaming environment to ease integration [6]. However, implementing PBL in Spain is not straightforward, mainly due to administrative and curriculum barriers [7].

This paper presents an application of PBL into the course Quantitative Methods of Industrial Process Management II (MQ2), taught at the Master's Degree in Industrial Engineering (MUEI) of the Technical University of Catalonia (UPC). It is a 4.5 ECTS course, compulsory for the Industrial Organisation branch students of MUEI and optional for the other branches. Every semester, around 40 students are enrolled.

1.1 Learning objectives and competencies

In MQ2, students learn to model and solve industrial organisation and management problems with exact and heuristic procedures. The learning objectives are:

- To model and solve classical combinatorial optimisation problems using exact and heuristic procedures.
- To develop ad hoc solving procedures for non-standard problems.

In addition, the competencies worked in the course include:

- Transversal. Group working.
- Basic. To develop ideas, in a research context.
- Basic. To apply concepts learnt into new and multidisciplinary contexts.
- Specific. To develop and apply analytic methods for decision making.

1.2 Teaching methodology

This course is based on PBL to favour learning of objectives and competencies [3]. There are 3 session typologies:

- In master classes, lecturers introduce the theoretical concepts of the course, using illustrative examples to ease understanding.
- In practical classes, lecturers guide students in applying theory concepts to solve small-size problems, encouraging critical reasoning.
- In competitive project, students develop an ad hoc heuristic to solve a real-based industrial organisation problem in 3-member groups (Section 2).

MQ2 has 7 modules: (1) mathematical programming, (2) combinatorial optimization, (3) heuristics, (4) enumerative searching procedures, (5) neighbourhood exploration algorithms, (6) matheuristics and hiperheuristics, and (7) real-based applications.

The final mark is calculated according to the competitive project (80%), as detailed in Section 2, deliveries during the practical classes (10%) and an exam to evaluate whether students have understood the practices or not (10%).

2 METHODOLOGY

The core of MQ2 is the competitive project. At the beginning of the semester, a real-based combinatorial optimization problem is proposed to students. The problem is enough complex to lead to a very high amount of feasible solutions, although only one (or a reduced set) is optimal. Over the course, students develop an ad hoc (meta/math/hiper)heuristic, based on the class concepts, and code it with standard language (Python, Java, C++, etc.). Examples of problems are: (a) assignment of boats to quays and containers to port locations or (b) path in a warehouse to pick up products for pallets to be sent to supermarkets.

Together with the problem statement, a set of test-instances is provided to students, each one representing a different combination of parameters of the problem, that can be used for testing purposes. The format of the instances and the results returned by the heuristics is defined beforehand and students adapt their codes accordingly. In addition, the results of the objective function obtained by a simple heuristic, developed by the lecturers, is also provided for the test-instances. This value represents the minimum quality threshold that will be considered acceptable for the evaluation. Finally, a testing programme is also provided to ensure the objective function is properly calculated, the results format is correct and avoid unnecessary mistakes during the evaluation.

The day of the evaluation, a set of 10 new exam-instances is provided to students (with the standard format). Using identical school computers, students launch their codes and solve the 10 instances in a maximum time of 5 minutes per instance. After 50 minutes, the results together with the code and a report, explaining the heuristic developed, must be delivered.

The evaluation of the competitive project is calculated based on the report (20%) and the average mark for the 10 exam-instances (80%), where each instance mark is:

- If the solution is better than the minimum quality threshold, the mark is 10 for the group getting the best solution and 7 for the worst (overcoming the threshold). A linear progression is considered for intermediate groups.
- If the solution is worse than the minimum quality threshold, the mark is 0.

The competitive environment forces students not to share their findings (ex.: strategies for developing heuristics), while being in a friendly-gaming environment.

In order to evaluate the perception of this activity by students, the students' satisfaction surveys carried out by the university are reviewed. At the end of each semester students can optionally give their opinion about the courses through an online university platform, logically anonymously and without the intervention of lecturers. These surveys are answered at the end of the lecturing period and before the exams period, to avoid the final marks influence the answers. The survey includes a quantitative assessment where students evaluate, on a 1-5 scale, lecturers and courses; and a quantitative assessment where they can express their opinion in a short text.

3 RESULTS

The evaluation of this activity is complex, since it was implemented during a Masters curriculum modification (September 2015), without the possibility of considering control and experimental groups. In addition, some sources of information are not available for all the semesters. Despite these limitations, Table 1 summarises the performance for some indicators before and after the competitive project, gathered from students' satisfaction surveys. Since surveys are optional, a variable number of answers is obtained each semester. However, approximately 30-40% of students answer the survey, i.e. around 12-16 students each semester. Before the competitive project here assessed, the course contents were the same and the teaching methodology was also based on master and practical classes, but the evaluation was done through traditional exams.

Table 1. Course performance before and after the competitive project

Indicator	Before	After	Variation
I1. Students' interest on the course (1-5 scale)	3.59	3.85	+7.2%
I2. Students' satisfaction on the course (1-5 scale)	3.52	3.44	-2.4%
I3. Students' average final mark (0-10 scale)	6.14	7.51	+22.3%
I4. Students abandoning the course (%)	9.9%	1.5%	-84.4%

The indicators I1 and I2 are compiled from students' surveys, carried out at the end of each semester. As observed, the interest on the course has significantly increased (+7.2%), although the satisfaction has slightly diminished (-2.4%). Examining the comments section in students' surveys, the main reason for not being more satisfied is that the competitive project requires from programming skills that many students do not have. Efforts are currently being made to address this issue. On the other hand, indicators I3 and I4 are calculated from the results of students after the course evaluation. As observed, the average mark has notably improved (+22.3%). This indicator is not robust since it compares two different evaluation methods, but assuming the course responsible has remained the same person, the rigorousness can be considered similar. Under this assumption, a notable increase in students' performance has been accomplished. Indeed, indicator I4 shows a very relevant diminution of abandonments and, through the comments section of students' surveys, a much higher dedication can be deduced.

4 CONCLUSION

This paper shows an example of PBL to teach complex engineering concepts, such as advanced quantitative methods to solve combinatorial optimisation problems (course MQ2). In general terms, the evaluation of PBL implementation is positive. Students invest more time to understand and apply the course contents and they show a higher interest. However, some limitations in the requisites to accomplish the competitive project still need to be addressed.

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